

Parkinson's Disease and Sleep –Key Insights

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OPEN ACCESS

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Received: 03-07-2025

Accepted: 23-07-2025

Available Online: 05-08-2025

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ABSTRACT

Parkinson's disease (PD) is characterized by motor symptoms such as bradykinesia, rest tremor, rigidity, and postural instability, alongside various non-motor symptoms. The prevalence of PD increases with age, particularly between ages 85 and 89, and exhibits a male predominance. Sleep disturbances affect 64% of PD patients, yet less than half report these issues to healthcare providers. Sleep disorders, including insomnia, restless legs syndrome (RLS), rapid eye movement (REM) sleep behavior disorder (RBD), excessive daytime sleepiness (EDS), sleep-disordered breathing (SDB), and circadian rhythm disorders, substantially worsen non-motor symptoms and reduce quality of life. Neurodegenerative processes and dopaminergic dysfunction play critical roles in these sleep disturbances. Additionally, medications, co-morbidities, and genetic factors contribute to disrupted sleep patterns in PD.

Keywords: Parkinson's disease, sleep disturbances, bradykinesia, rest tremor, rigidity, postural instability, non-motor symptoms, insomnia, restless legs syndrome, rapid eye movement sleep behavior disorder, excessive daytime sleepiness, sleep-disordered breathing, circadian rhythm disorders, dopaminergic dysfunction, neurodegenerative processes

INTRODUCTION

The hallmark of Parkinson's disease (PD), which was first described by James Parkinson, includes bradykinesia, rest tremor, rigidity and postural instability, and a host of other motor and non-motor symptoms¹. The prevalence increases with age, peaking between ages 85 and 89 years, with a male predominance. Most cases of idiopathic, however there are known genetic and environmental contributions². The Braak hypothesis is the model most frequently used to explain the neuropathological course of Parkinson's disease. This concept proposes that the medulla and olfactory bulb are where the disease begins. This early pathology is linked to symptoms including diminished smell and rapid eye movement sleep behaviour disorder, which occurs before the development of the classical symptoms³.

Sleep disturbances have been observed in 64% of patients with PD⁴. However less than half of sleep issues are reported to doctors and receive adequate care. Sleep disturbances in PD will raise the burden of non-motor symptoms in addition to motor dysfunction which can lead to reduced cognitive performance, a higher risk of falls, and a lower quality of life⁵. In addition this will also bring significant socio-economic consequences. Sleep is one significant disease-modifying element in this disease.

The most reported sleep disorders in PD include insomnia, restless legs syndrome (RLS), rapid eye movement (Rapid Eye Movement, sleep behaviour disorders (RBD), excessive daytime sleepiness (EDS) sleep disordered breathing (SDB) and circadian rhythm disorders⁶.

Pathophysiology

Sleep disturbances in PD are intricately linked to the neurodegenerative process itself, influenced by the deposition of both alpha synuclein in the brain region that regulate sleep such as the locus coeruleus, raphe nuclei, paramillary and

posterior hypothalamic nuclei, amygdala, and thalamus. Disruption of these structures and their interconnected circuits likely plays a critical role in the sleep disturbances commonly seen in PD, including insomnia, EDS and RBD. Additionally, motor symptoms like RLS, which significantly affect nocturnal sleep, and breathing disorders such as sleep apnoea, further contribute to the fragmented sleep-wake cycle seen in PD patients⁷. These combined factors result in severe disruptions to sleep quality and overall circadian rhythm in PD.

The dopaminergic system is crucial in regulating the sleep-wake cycle. Dopamine within the basal ganglia facilitates sleep through D2 receptors, whereas the dopaminergic pathways outside the basal ganglia support wakefulness via D1 and D2 receptors⁸. So dopaminergic dysfunction in PD can lead to sleep disturbances.

The neuropeptide orexin plays a key role in promoting arousal, and its deficiency may contribute EDS, as well as sleep attacks and narcolepsy-like symptoms in PD⁹. Disruptions in the circadian rhythm have also been observed in PD, which likely contribute to EDS. Patients exhibit a dampened, though still intact, circadian rhythm, characterized by a reduced amplitude in the melatonin cycle and lower overall 24-hour melatonin levels¹⁰.

Histological studies have revealed pathological changes in both the suprachiasmatic nucleus and its afferent pathways originating from the photosensitive retinal ganglion cells in patients with PD which can lead to circadian rhythm disorders¹¹.

In addition to the impairments in brain function and neurotransmitter activity, several other significant factors also contribute to the sleep disturbances in PD. These include medications like dopamine agonists causing day time sleepiness and 'sleep attacks', antidepressants like SSRIs (Selective Serotonin Reuptake Inhibitors), SNRIs (Serotonin and Norepinephrine reuptake inhibitors), and TCAs (Tricyclic Antidepressants) used to treat the co morbid mood disorders can alter sleep patterns¹². Other contributing factors are co-morbidities, PD-related symptoms such as nocturnal akinesia that disrupt sleep, and genetic factors that may predispose individuals to specific sleep and wakefulness disturbances¹³. Furthermore, the clinical profile of PD-RLS patients, marked by more severe non-motor symptoms, indicates that neurotransmitter systems beyond dopamine may be involved in the development of PD-RLS. This suggests that factors other than dopaminergic dysfunction could play a role in its etiology, necessitating further exploration of these complex interactions¹⁴.

Clinical features

Insomnia

Insomnia is defined by the International Classification of Sleep Disorders, Third Edition, as difficulty initiating sleep, difficulty maintaining sleep, and/or early morning awakenings¹⁵. It is reported in 44% of PD patients and is closely associated with longer disease duration, higher Levodopa equivalent dose, and more severe depression¹⁶.

Rapid eye movement sleep behaviour disorders

RBD is a parasomnia marked by abnormal behaviours and the loss of muscle atonia during REM sleep. This can include vocalizations, jerks, and other motor actions that typically align with the content of dreams with most of the dreams being violent or aggressive, so that they can hurt themselves or bed partners¹⁷.

Meta-analyses report showed that the pooled prevalence of RBD in PD as 42.3%¹⁸ and 46%¹⁹, with RBD occurrence associated with older age, longer disease duration, higher levodopa equivalent daily dose, worse motor and autonomic symptoms, and poorer quality of life^{18,19}.

Motor manifestations in PD with RBD seem to differ from those without RBD, exhibiting a non-tremor predominant phenotype and perhaps more postural instability and falls²⁰. Interestingly, both video-polysomnography (PSG) analysis and reports from bed partners reveal a paradoxical alleviation of parkinsonism during complex RBD episodes. Movements during the episodes were faster, stronger, and smoother and speech was more louder. These suggest a transient restoration of motor function during REM sleep, potentially via bypassing the extrapyramidal system²¹. Additionally, RBD in PD is associated with visual hallucinations²². It also serves as an early marker of neurodegenerative disease underscoring its potential role in early diagnosis and monitoring of disease progression²³

Sleep waling which is an NREM parasomnia has also been reported in PD patients. In most cases there was associated RBD. So there is still a need for polysomnographic confirmation of these episodes^{24,25}.

Obstructive Sleep Apnoea

OSA is a sleep-related breathing disorder caused by the repetitive collapse of the upper airway, leading to intermittent hypoxia and impaired ventilation during sleep. Diagnostic criteria for OSA include more than 15 respiratory events per

hour, or more than 5 events per hour when accompanied by typical symptoms such as snoring, fatigue, EDS, or co-morbid conditions like hypertension, coronary artery disease, or stroke²⁶. It is estimated that 20% to 60% of PD patients have concomitant OSA²⁷. Studies have shown that PD patients with OSA exhibit worse cognitive function²⁸.

Excessive Daytime Sleepiness

EDS can be defined as the tendency to nod or fall asleep in various situations during daytime. The prevalence of EDS in PD is 35%, with a higher incidence observed in older patients, those with longer disease duration, more severe motor and autonomic symptoms, higher levodopa equivalent daily dose, reduced autonomic functions, and more pronounced neuropsychiatric symptoms¹⁶. Key factors contributing to EDS include motor complications, such as wearing-off symptoms, the dosage of antiparkinsonian medications, and sleep-disordered breathing. In some cases, severe forms of EDS resembling narcolepsy may occur in PD patients²⁹.

Restless Legs Syndrome

RLS is characterized by an uncontrollable urge to move the legs, often accompanied by sensory symptoms and discomfort in the lower limbs, particularly around the ankles and knees which gets worsened during periods of rest and tend to subside with movement³⁰. However other body parts like arms, abdomen, hips, trunk, genitalia, and even the head and face can also be involved^{31,32,33}. It may also serve as a potential preclinical marker of PD³⁴.

In a recent meta-analysis the pooled prevalence of RLS in PD was found to be 20% and was associated with female sex, a mixed motor phenotype, more severe motor symptoms, and non-motor symptoms like RBD, greater cognitive and autonomic dysfunction, increased neuropsychiatric symptoms, higher levels of fatigue, EDS, and poorer sleep quality and quality of life³⁵.

Periodic leg movement of sleep, which are stereotyped movements of the foot and leg typically recurring every 20-40sec mainly during the first part of night during NREM sleep, occur in more than 80% patient with RLS. However they are also well described in PD in the absence of RLS³⁶.

Circadian rhythm disorder

Circadian rhythm disorders involve persistent or recurring sleep disturbances caused by disruptions in the circadian system or a mismatch between the body's internal circadian rhythm and external, socially imposed sleep-wake schedules³⁷. It can lead to an advanced or delayed onset of sleep in patients and create disruption of normal sleep and wake times⁶. It has been linked to decreased sleep quality during the night, as well as diminished daytime alertness and cognitive function³⁸.

Diagnosis

Commonly employed methods for detecting sleep disorders in PD include a comprehensive medical history, sleep quality questionnaires, and polysomnography. Recommended questionnaires, among others, include the Parkinson's Disease Sleep Scale (PDSS), the Pittsburgh Sleep Quality Index (PSQI), the Epworth Sleepiness Scale (ESS), and the Stanford Sleepiness Scale (SSS)³⁹. The multiple sleep latency test (MSLT) is an objective assessment of daytime function in patients with chronic insomnia⁴⁰. Actigraphy or dim light melatonin onset may prove useful if a circadian disorder, such as delayed or advanced sleep phase syndrome or non-24-h sleep-wake disorder is suspected⁴¹.

Treatment

The treatment should begin with education on sleep hygiene and non-pharmacological interventions. Pharmacological treatment typically starts by optimizing antiparkinsonian medications. Afterwards, medications tailored to the specific type of sleep disorder are introduced. Managing sleep issues in PD is a continuous process that requires careful attention to choosing the most effective treatment with the fewest side effects for lasting results⁴².

Insomnia

Effective treatment for insomnia, whether pharmacological or behavioural, requires accurate identification of the insomnia type (initial, maintenance, or terminal) and the underlying factors. Levodopa-carbidopa controlled-release (LD-CR) may improve sleep-associated motor symptoms in PD, but evidence on its effect on sleep parameters is limited. Studies showed some improvement in nocturnal akinesia with LD-CR, but no significant changes in total sleep time or sleep fragmentation⁴³.

Certain studies have shown that dopamine agonists like ropinirole and pramipexole have shown modest improvements in insomnia symptoms. Ropinirole prolonged release (PR) improved nocturnal symptoms and sleep quality in advanced PD

patients⁴⁴ while pramipexole sustained release (SR) also demonstrated beneficial effects⁴⁵. Similarly, rotigotine patches have significantly improved sleep in PD patients with early-morning motor symptoms⁴⁶.

Observational studies suggest that treatments providing consistent dopaminergic stimulation, such as apomorphine and levodopa gel infusion, can enhance sleep quality and reduce sleep fragmentation in advanced PD. These findings suggest that medications providing stable dopamine levels may be key in managing PD-related insomnia^{47,48}.

A prospective observational by Schettino C et al showed that Rasagiline, added to levodopa significantly improved sleep latency and total sleep time⁴⁹.

Eszopiclone, FDA (Food and Drug Administration) approved for the treatment of sleep initiation and maintenance insomnia, has shown significant benefits in PD patients. A randomized controlled trial (RCT) involving 30 PD patients found that a dose of 2 to 3 mg of eszopiclone significantly improved several sleep parameters, including reduced nocturnal awakenings and improved sleep quality ratings. However, 13% of patients experienced side effects such as daytime sleepiness and dizziness⁵⁰.

Doxepin, at doses of 3-6 mg, was tested in a trial involving 18 participants. Compared to placebo, doxepin (10 mg) resulted in significant improvements in insomnia severity index scores, sleep quality, and fatigue. However, 50% of participants reported side effects such as fatigue, orthostatic dizziness, and nausea⁵¹.

A meta-analysis of 7 studies found that melatonin significantly improved subjective sleep quality in PD patients.⁴² In individuals with PD and psychosis, pimavanserin, a serotonin 5HT_{2A} receptor inverse agonist/antagonist, has shown promise in improving insomnia symptoms. In two RCTs, pimavanserin (34 mg) significantly improved night time complaints compared to placebo, with a notable reduction in insomnia-related issue⁵².

Nonpharmacological treatments, such as cognitive behavioral therapy for insomnia (CBT-I) and bright light therapy (BLT), also remain valuable approaches in managing sleep disturbances in PD^{53,54}. Exercise, including Tai Chi, offer useful non-drug options for managing sleep problems in PD⁵⁵.

Studies have shown Deep Brain Stimulation (DBS) significant improvements in sleep quality, sleep latency, sleep efficiency, sleep duration, and insomnia symptoms in PD patients after treatment^{56,57}.

RBD

First-line interventions for managing RBD should include a thorough evaluation of environmental safety. To mitigate the risk of injury during episodes, recommendations may include the installation of bed rails to prevent falls from bed. Additionally, it is crucial to remove any dangerous objects or weapons from the patient's immediate surroundings, particularly from within or near the bedroom, to reduce the potential for harm during violent dream enactment behaviors^{58,59}.

In the treatment of RBD associated PD, several pharmacological interventions have been explored. Clonazepam is one of the most commonly used medications, demonstrating effectiveness in reducing the frequency of violent dream enactment behaviours and improving symptoms in a majority of patients^{59,60}. However, long-term use can be associated with side effects such as morning sedation, confusion, dizziness, and falls, particularly in older patients or those with neurodegenerative conditions⁶¹. Despite some positive case series, the results of large-scale clinical trials, including a recent placebo-controlled study, have been inconclusive regarding the efficacy of clonazepam in treating RBD in PD⁶².

An RCT suggested that exogenous melatonin, can be considered as a potential monotherapy or adjunctive therapy for patients with RBD in patients with neurodegenerative disorders⁶³. However certain RCTs failed to demonstrate a positive effect of melatonin on RD in PD⁶⁴.

Pramipexole, paroxetine, donepezil, and rivastigmine may help in some refractory cases of RBD, though evidence remains inconclusive due to a lack of large RCTs⁶⁵. Rivastigmine has shown some promise in reducing RBD episodes in small studies of PD and mild cognitive impairment patients⁶⁶.

Medications that can worsen RBD, including SSRIs, SNRIs, and tricyclic antidepressants, should be discontinued or avoided⁶⁷. Alcohol use can also exacerbate RBD episodes and should be limited in individuals who show a correlation between alcohol use and RBD⁶⁸.

"Pseudo-RBD" can occur in patients with OSA, leading to agitated arousals due to obstructive events⁶⁹. Diagnosing and treating OSA with CPAP

(Continuous Positive Airway Pressure) is crucial in patients with both OSA and co morbid RBD to reduce nocturnal behaviours⁷⁰.

Restless Legs Syndrome

If RLS is mild, it can often be managed through lifestyle changes alone. Before initiating pharmacological treatment, it is important to assess the frequency, duration, and impact of symptoms on the patient's quality of life. Additionally, screening for secondary causes is essential, including chronic renal failure, deficiencies in iron, vitamin B12, and folic acid, as well as evaluating serum glucose and HbA1C levels. Serum ferritin should be measured, and if it is below 50–75 µg/mL or transferrin saturation is under 20%, oral iron supplementation is recommended. It is also recommended to discontinue medications that may worsen RLS, such as antidopaminergic drugs, antihistamines, and antidepressants (with the exception of bupropion)⁷¹.

Therapeutic options include calcium channel alpha-2-delta ligands (pregabalin, gabapentin, enacarbil) and low-dose dopamine agonists⁷². However dopamine agonist may cause augmentation of RLS. To prevent that long-acting DAs should be preferred⁷¹.

In cases that are resistant to other treatments, low doses of opioids, such as long-acting oxycodone or methadone, may be considered, but should be avoided in patients with a high risk of addiction or those with pre-existing conditions such as severe constipation, sleep apnea syndrome, or prolonged QTc. Additionally, patients may find temporary relief by rubbing or massaging the affected limbs, bathing in hot or cold water, engaging in physical activity, or distracting themselves with mental exercises, such as reading an interesting book when symptoms first appear⁷³.

DBS of the subthalamic nucleus has shown to provide symptom relief in most PD patients with RLS⁷⁴.

Excessive Daytime Sleepiness (EDS)

The first step in the management of EDS is to identify and address any potential sleep disorders that may interfere with nocturnal sleep. Additionally, it is important to review and adjust medications that could contribute to hypersomnia, such as antidepressants, antipsychotics, or sedatives. Educating patients on proper sleep hygiene is also a crucial aspect of treatment. When it comes to medication management, dopamine agonists have been found to cause more EDS compared to levodopa, with the degree of sleepiness directly related to the dose of the dopamine agonists. On the other hand, medications like selegiline, amantadine, and entacapone have shown no significant impact on EDS^{75, 76, 77, 78}.

The pharmacological treatment options include, modafinil and caffeine which are the primary wake-promoting agents⁷⁹.

Obstructive Sleep Apnoea

PD-related upper airway dysfunction may worsen OSA by reducing airway stability. A study showed that long-acting levodopa at night helped reduce OSA severity in PD⁸⁰.

A short-term randomized crossover trial in PD showed that CPAP treatment for OSA improved objective daytime sleepiness, sleep quality, AHI (Apnoea Hypopnoea index), and oxygen saturation⁸¹. Another cohort study demonstrated improvement in non-motor symptoms overall, subjective sleep quality, anxiety, and cognitive function with CPAP treatment⁸². However due to cognitive deficits, motor issues, and other factors like nocturia, anxiety, and RBD, many patients discontinue treatment⁸³.

Alternatives like mandibular advancement devices (MAD) have shown promise, improving sleep and apnoea severity, with better compliance compared to CPAP⁸⁴.

Circadian rhythm disorder

Light therapy demonstrates promising results in improving sleep and alertness in PD, with positive effects on sleep, mood, and other non-motor symptoms associated with the condition^{85, 86}. Other treatment options including physical exercise and melatonin may be beneficial but have not been systematically evaluated in patients with PD⁶.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, sleep disorders in PD significantly impact patients' quality of life and are closely linked to motor and non-motor symptoms. Conditions such as insomnia, excessive daytime sleepiness, restless legs syndrome, and REM sleep behaviour disorder are common in PD. These disturbances often worsen with disease progression and complicate the management of PD. While interventions such as dopaminergic therapy optimization and sleep hygiene education are essential, pharmacological treatments show variable efficacy and may have side effects. Ongoing research is needed to better understand the pathophysiology and develop more effective, personalized management strategies for sleep disturbances in PD.

REFERENCES

1. J. Parkinson's disease: clinical features and diagnosis. *J Neurol Neurosurg Psychiatry*. 2008;79(4):368–76.
2. GBD 2016 Parkinson's Disease Collaborators. Global, regional, and national burden of Parkinson's disease, 1990-2016: a systematic analysis for the Global Burden of Disease Study 2016. *Lancet Neurol*. 2018;17(11):939-53.
3. Braak H, Del Tredici K, Rüb U, de Vos RA, Jansen Steur EN, Braak E. Staging of brain pathology related to sporadic Parkinson's disease. *Neurobiol Aging*. 2003;24(2):197-211.
4. Barone P, Antonini A, Colosimo C, Marconi R, Morgante L, Avarello TP, Bottacchi E, Cannas A, Ceravolo G, Ceravolo R, Cicarelli G. The PRIAMO study: a multicenter assessment of nonmotor symptoms and their impact on quality of life in Parkinson's disease. *Movement disorders: official journal of the Movement Disorder Society*. 2009 Aug 15;24(11):1641-9.
5. Park S, Kim R, Shin JH, Kim HJ, Paek SH, Jeon B. The probable REM sleep behavior disorder negatively affects health-related quality of life in Parkinson's disease with bilateral subthalamic nucleus stimulation. *Parkinsonism & Related Disorders*. 2020 Dec 1;81:136-9.
6. Zuzuáregui JR, During EH. Sleep issues in Parkinson's disease and their management. *Neurotherapeutics*. 2020 Oct 1;17(4):1480-94.
7. Kalaitzakis ME, Gentleman SM, Pearce RKB. Disturbed sleep in Parkinson's disease: Anatomical and pathological correlates. *Neuropathol Appl Neurobiol*. 2013;39(6):644-653.
8. Vetrivelan R, Qiu M-H, Chang C, Lu J. Role of Basal Ganglia in sleep-wake regulation: Neural circuitry and clinical significance. *Front Neuroanat*. 2010;4:145.
9. Liu C, Xue Y, Liu MF, Wang Y, Chen L. Orexin and Parkinson's disease: a protective neuropeptide with therapeutic potential. *Neurochem Int*. 2020;138:104754.
10. Videnovic A, Noble C, Reid KJ, Peng J, Turek FW, Marconi A, Rademaker AW, Simuni T, Zadikoff C, Zee PC. Circadian melatonin rhythm and excessive daytime sleepiness in Parkinson disease. *JAMA neurology*. 2014 Apr 1;71(4):463-9.
11. De Pablo-Fernández E, Courtney R, Warner TT, Holton JL. A histologic study of the circadian system in Parkinson disease, multiple system atrophy, and progressive supranuclear palsy. *JAMA Neurol*. 2018 Aug 1;75(8):1008-1012.
12. Valko PO, Waldvogel D, Weller M, Bassetti CL, Held U, Baumann CR. Fatigue and excessive daytime sleepiness in idiopathic Parkinson's disease differently correlate with motor symptoms, depression and dopaminergic treatment. *Eur J Neurol*. 2010;17(12):1428–1436.
13. Trenkwalder C, Hogl B. Sleep in Parkinson syndromes. *Handb Clin Neurol*. 2007;83:365–76.
14. Maggi G, Barone A, Mastromarino C, Santangelo G, Vitale C. Prevalence and clinical profile of patients with restless legs syndrome in Parkinson's disease: A meta-analysis. *Sleep Med*. 2024 Jul 15.
15. Sateia MJ. International classification of sleep disorders-third edition: highlights and modifications. *Chest*. 2014;146:1387–94.
16. Maggi G, Vitale C, Cerciello F, Santangelo G. Sleep and wakefulness disturbances in Parkinson's disease: A meta-analysis on prevalence and clinical aspects of REM sleep behavior disorder, excessive daytime sleepiness and insomnia. *Sleep Med Rev*. 2023 Apr 1;68:101759.
17. Jiang H, Huang J, Shen Y, Guo S, Wang L, Han C, Liu L, Ma K, Xia Y, Li J, Xu X, Xiong N, Wang T. RBD and neurodegenerative diseases. *Mol Neurobiol*. 2017 May;54(4):2997-3006.
18. Zhang J, Xu CY, Liu J. Meta-analysis on the prevalence of REM sleep behavior disorder symptoms in Parkinson's disease. *BMC Neurol*. 2017 Dec;17:1-6.
19. Zhang X, Sun X, Wang J, Tang L, Xie A. Prevalence of rapid eye movement sleep behavior disorder (RBD) in Parkinson's disease: A meta and meta-regression analysis. *Neurol Sci*. 2017 Jan;38:163-70.
20. Postuma RB, Gagnon JF, Vendette M, Charland K, Montplaisir J. REM sleep behaviour disorder in Parkinson's disease is associated with specific motor features. *J Neurol Neurosurg Psychiatry*. 2008;79:1117–1121.
21. De Cock VC, Vidailhet M, Leu S, Teixeira A, Apartis E, Elbaz A, Roze E, Willer JC, Derenne JP, Agid Y, Arnulf I. Restoration of normal motor control in Parkinson's disease during REM sleep. *Brain*. 2007;130:450–456.
22. Nomura T, Inoue Y, Mitani H, Kawahara R, Miyake M, Nakashima K. Visual hallucinations as REM sleep behavior disorders in patients with Parkinson's disease. *Mov Disord*. 2003 Jul;18(7):812-7.
23. Postuma RB, Iranzo A, Hu M, Högl B, Boeve BF, Manni R, Oertel WH, Arnulf I, Ferini-Strambi L, Puligheddu M, Antelmi E. Risk and predictors of dementia and parkinsonism in idiopathic REM sleep behaviour disorder: a multicentre study. *Brain*. 2019 Mar 1;142(3):744-59.
24. Poryazova R, Waldvogel D, Bassetti CL. Sleepwalking in patients with Parkinson's disease. *Arch Neurol*. 2007;64(10):1524-1527.
25. Jancovics J, Tolosa E. Sleep and fatigue in Parkinson's disease. In: *Parkinson's disease and movement disorders*. 6th ed. Vol. 2. Wolters Kluwer; 2015. p. 1097.

26. Kapur VK, Auckley DH, Chowdhuri S, Kuhlmann DC, Mehra R, Ramar K, et al. Clinical practice guideline for diagnostic testing for adult obstructive sleep apnea: an American Academy of Sleep Medicine clinical practice guideline. *J Clin Sleep Med.* 2017;13:479-504.
27. Da Silva-Júnior FP, do Prado GF, Barbosa ER, Tufik S, Togeiro SM. Sleep disordered breathing in Parkinson's disease: A critical appraisal. *Sleep Med Rev.* 2014;18:173-178
28. Harmell AL, Neikrug AB, Palmer BW, Avanzino JA, Liu L, Maglione JE, Natarajan L, Corey-Bloom J, Loredó JS, Ancoli-Israel S. Obstructive sleep apnea and cognition in Parkinson's disease. *Sleep Med.* 2016 May;21:28-34.
29. Poryazova R, Benninger D, Waldvogel D, Bassetti CL. Excessive daytime sleepiness in Parkinson's disease: characteristics and determinants. *European neurology.* 2010 Jan 16;63(3):129-35.
30. Earley CJ. Restless legs syndrome. *New England Journal of Medicine.* 2003 May 22;348(21):2103-9.
31. Balgetir F, Gönen M, Berilgen A, Aytaç E, Demir CF, Müngen B. Restless legs syndrome affecting the head region: "restless head syndrome". *Neurol Sci.* 2022 Apr;1-6.
32. Sun Z, Tan Y, Li Z, Yang L, Sun X, Du Y, Chen Y. Teaching Video NeuroImage: Restless abdomen: A rare variant of restless legs syndrome. *Neurology.* 2022 May 17;98(20):858-9.
33. Suzuki K, Suzuki S, Miyamoto M, Miyamoto T, Matsubara T, Nozawa N, Arikawa T, Nakajima I, Hirata K. Involvement of legs and other body parts in patients with restless legs syndrome and its variants. *J Neurol Sci.* 2019 Dec 15;407:116519.
34. Chaudhuri KR, Healy DG, Schapira AH, National Institute for Clinical Excellence. Non-motor symptoms of Parkinson's disease: diagnosis and management. *Lancet Neurol.* 2006 Mar;5(3):235-45.
35. Maggi G, Barone A, Mastromarino C, Santangelo G, Vitale C. Prevalence and clinical profile of patients with restless legs syndrome in Parkinson's disease: A meta-analysis. *Sleep Med.* 2024 Jul 15.
36. Wetter T, Collado-Seidel V, Pollmacher T, Yassouridis A, Trenkwalder C. Sleep and periodic leg movement patterns in drug-free patients with Parkinson's disease and multiple system atrophy. *SLEEP-NEW YORK-.* 2000 May 1;23(3):361-8.
37. Darien IL. The diagnostic criteria of the American Academy of Sleep Medicine. The international classification of sleep disorders. 3rd ed. Darien, IL: American Academy of Sleep Medicine. 2014
38. Buysse, D.J., Monk, T.H., Carrier, J., Begley, A., 2005. Circadian patterns of sleep, sleepiness, and performance in older and younger adults. *Sleep* 28, 1365–1376
39. Jongwanasiri S, Prayoonwivat N, Pisarnpong A, Srivannichapoom P, Chotinaiwattarakul W. Evaluation of sleep disorders in Parkinson's disease: A comparison between physician diagnosis and self-administered questionnaires. *J Med Assoc Thai.* 2014;97(3 Suppl 3):S68–S77.
40. Zhang L, Zhao ZX. Objective and subjective measures for sleep disorders. *Neuroscience bulletin.* 2008 Feb 1;23(4):236.
41. Högl B, Wetter TC, Trenkwalder C. Pathophysiology, clinical aspects and therapy of sleep disorders in Parkinson disease. *Der Nervenarzt.* 2001 Jun 1;72(6):416-24.
42. Ma H, Yan J, Sun W, Jiang M, Zhang Y. Melatonin treatment for sleep disorders in Parkinson's disease: a meta-analysis and systematic review. *Front Aging Neurosci.* 2022 Feb 4;14:784314.
43. S, Herzog J, Witt K, Deuschl G, Volkmann J. Effect of controlled-release levodopa on the microstructure of sleep in Parkinson's disease. *Eur J Neurol.* 2011;18:590-6.
44. Pahwa R, Stacy MA, Factor SA, et al. Ropinirole 24-hour prolonged release randomized controlled study in advanced Parkinson's disease. *Neurology.* 2007;68(14):1108-15.
45. Poewe WH, Rascol O, Quinn N, et al. Efficacy of pramipexole and transdermal rotigotine in advanced Parkinson's disease: a double-blind, double-dummy, randomised controlled trial. *Lancet Neurol.* 2007;6(7):513-20.
46. Trenkwalder C, Kies B, Rudzinska M, et al. Rotigotine effects on early morning motor function and sleep in Parkinson's disease: a double-blind, randomized, placebo-controlled study (RECOVER). *Mov Disord.* 2011;26(1):90-9.
47. Martinez-Martin P, Reddy P, Katzenschlager R, et al. EuroInf: a multicenter comparative observational study of apomorphine and levodopa infusion in Parkinson's disease. *Mov Disord.* 2015;30(4):510-6.
48. Standaert DG, Rodriguez RL, Slevin JT, et al. Effect of levodopa-carbidopa intestinal gel on non-motor symptoms in patients with advanced Parkinson's disease. *Mov Disord Clin Pract.* 2017;4(6):829-37.
49. Schettino C, Dato C, Capaldo G, Sampaolo S, Di Iorio G, Melone MA. Rasagiline for sleep disorders in patients with Parkinson's disease: a pro-spective observational study. *Neuropsychiatr Dis Treat* (2016) 12:2497–502.
50. Menza M, Dobkin RD, Marin H, et al. Treatment of insomnia in Parkinson's disease: a controlled trial of eszopiclone and placebo. *Mov Disord.* 2010;25(11):1708-14.
51. Rios Romanets S, Creti L, Fichten C, et al. Doxepin and cognitive behavioural therapy for insomnia in patients with Parkinson's disease—a randomized study. *Parkinsonism Relat Disord.* 2013;19(7):670-5.

52. Patel N, LeWitt P, Neikrug AB, Kessler P, Coate B, Ancoli-Israel S. Nighttime sleep and daytime sleepiness improved with pimavanserin during treatment of Parkinson's disease psychosis. *Clin Psychopharmacol.* 2018;41(2):210-5.
53. Videnovic A, Klerman EB, Wang W, Marconi A, Kuhta T, Zee PC. Timed light therapy for sleep and daytime sleepiness associated with Parkinson disease: a randomized clinical trial. *JAMA Neurol.* 2017;74(4):411-8.
54. Martino JK, Freelance CB, Willis GL. The effect of light exposure on insomnia and nocturnal movement in Parkinson's disease: an open label, retrospective, longitudinal study. *Sleep Med.* 2018;44:24-31
55. Yang JH, Wang YQ, Ye SQ, Cheng YG, Chen Y, Feng XZ. The effects of group-based versus individual-based Tai Chi training on nonmotor symptoms in patients with mild to moderate Parkinson's disease: a randomized controlled pilot trial. *Parkinsons Dis.* 2017;2017:8562867.
56. Sharma VD, Sengupta S, Chitnis S, Amara AW. Deep brain stimulation and sleep-wake disturbances in Parkinson disease: a review. *Front Neurol.* 2018;9:697.
57. Eugster L, Bargiotas P, Bassetti CL, Schuepbach WM. Deep brain stimulation and sleep-wake functions in Parkinson's disease: a systematic review. *Parkinsonism Relat Disord.* 2016;32:12–19.
58. Jung Y, Louis EK. Treatment of REM Sleep Behavior Disorder. *Curr Treat Options Neurol.* 2016;18(11):50. doi: 10.1007/s11940-016-0433-2. PubMed PMID: 27752878.
59. Aurora RN, Zak RS, Maganti RK, Auerbach SH, Casey KR, Chowdhuri S, Karippot A, Ramar K, Kristo DA, Morgenthaler TI. Best practice guide for the treatment of REM sleep behavior disorder (RBD). *J Clin Sleep Med.* 2010 Feb 15;6(1):85-95.
60. Li SX, Lam SP, Zhang J, et al. A prospective, naturalistic follow-up study of treatment outcomes with clonazepam in rapid eye movement sleep behavior disorder. *Sleep Med.* 2016;21:114–120.
61. Anderson KN, Shneerson JM. Drug treatment of REM sleep behavior disorder: the use of drug therapies other than clonazepam. *J Clin Sleep Med.* 2009;5(3):235–239.
62. Shin C, Park H, Lee WW, et al. Clonazepam for probable REM sleep behavior disorder in Parkinson's disease: A randomized placebo-controlled trial. *J Neurol Sci.* 2019;401:81–86.
63. Zhang W, Chen X, Su S, Jia Q, Ding T, Zhu Z, et al. Exogenous melatonin for sleep disorders in neurodegenerative diseases: a meta-analysis of randomized clinical trials. *Neurol Sci.* 2016;37:57–65.
64. Gilat M, Coeytaux Jackson A, Marshall NS, Hammond D, Mullins AE, Hall JM, Fang BAM, Yee BJ, Wong KKH, Grunstein RR, Lewis SJG. Melatonin for rapid eye movement sleep behavior disorder in Parkinson's disease: A randomised controlled trial. *Mov Disord.* 2020 Feb;35(2):344-349.
65. Sasai T, Matsuura M, Inoue Y. Factors associated with the effect of pramipexole on symptoms of idiopathic REM sleep behavior disorder. *Parkinsonism Relat Disord.* 2013;19:153–7.
66. Di Giacomo R, Fasano A, Quaranta D, Della Marca G, Bove F, Bentivoglio AR. Rivastigmine as alternative treatment for refractory REM behavior disorder in Parkinson's disease. *Mov Disord* (2012) 27:559–61.
67. Schenck CH, Mahowald MW. Rapid eye movement sleep parasomnias. *Neurol Clin.* 2005;23(4):1107–26.
68. Ma C, Pavlova M, Li J, et al. Alcohol consumption and probable rapid eye movement sleep behavior disorder. *Ann Clin Transl Neurol.* 2018;5(10):1176–83.
69. Bugalho P, Mendonça M, Barbosa R, Salavisa M. The influence of sleep disordered breathing in REM sleep behavior disorder. *Sleep Med.* 2017;37:210–5.
70. Gabrylska A, Roguski A, Simpson G, Maschauer EL, Morrison I, Riha RL. Prevalence of obstructive sleep apnoea in REM behaviour disorder: response to continuous positive airway pressure therapy. *Sleep Breath.* 2018;22(3):825–30.
71. Garcia-Borreguero, D., Silber, M.H., Winkelmann, J.W., Högl, B., Bainbridge, J., Buchfuhrer, M., Hadjigeorgiou, G., Inoue, Y., Manconi, M., Oertel, W. and Ondo, W., 2016. Guidelines for the first-line treatment of restless legs syndrome/Willis–Ekbom disease, prevention and treatment of dopaminergic augmentation: a combined task force of the IRLSSG, EURLSSG, and the RLS-foundation. *Sleep medicine*, 21, pp.1-11.
72. Falup-Pecurariu C, Muntean ML, Ungureanu L, Murasan I, Popławska-Domaszewicz K, Chaudhuri KR, Diaconu S. Pharmacological and non-pharmacological management of sleep disturbances in Parkinson's disease: If, when, and how. *Expert Opin Pharmacother.* 2024;25(16):2135-2149.
73. Klingelhofer L, Cova I, Gupta S, Chaudhuri KR. A review of current treatment strategies for restless legs syndrome (Willis–Ekbom disease). *Clinical medicine.* 2014 Oct 1;14(5):520-4.
74. Dulski J, Wąż P, Konkel A, Grabowski K, Libionka W, Schinwelski M, Sitek EJ, Sławek J. The Impact of Subthalamic Deep Brain Stimulation on Restless Legs Syndrome in Parkinson's Disease. *Neuromodulation: Technology at the Neural Interface.* 2022 Aug 1;25(6):904-10.
75. Zesiewicz TA, Hauser RA. Sleep attacks and dopamine agonists for Parkinson's disease: what is currently known?. *CNS drugs.* 2003 Jul;17:593-600.

76. Razmy A, Lang AE, Shapiro CM. Predictors of impaired daytime sleep and wakefulness in patients with Parkinson disease treated with older (ergot) vs newer (nonergot) dopamine agonists. *Archives of Neurology*. 2004 Jan 1;61(1):97-102.
77. Paus S, Brecht HM, Köster J, Seeger G, Klockgether T, Wüllner U. Sleep attacks, daytime sleepiness, and dopamine agonists in Parkinson's disease. *Movement Disorders*. 2003 Jun;18(6):659-67.
78. Valko PO, Waldvogel D, Weller M, Bassetti CL, Held U, Baumann CR. Fatigue and excessive daytime sleepiness in idiopathic Parkinson's disease differently correlate with motor symptoms, depression and dopaminergic treatment. *European journal of neurology*. 2010 Dec;17(12):1428-36.
79. Falup-Pecurariu C, Muntean ML, Ungureanu L, Murasan I, Popławska-Domaszewicz K, Chaudhuri KR, Diaconu S. Pharmacological and non-pharmacological management of sleep disturbances in Parkinson's disease: If, when, and how. *Expert Opin Pharmacother*. 2024;25(16):2135-214
80. Gros P, Mery VP, Lafontaine A-L, Robinson A, Benedetti A, Kimoff RJ, Kaminska M. Obstructive sleep apnea in Parkinson's disease patients: Effect of Sinemet CR taken at bedtime. *Sleep Breath*. 2016;20:205–12.
81. Neikrug AB, Liu L, Avanzino JA, Maglione JE, Natarajan L, Bradley L, Maugeri A, Corey-Bloom J, Palmer BW, Loreda JS, et al. Continuous positive airway pressure improves sleep and daytime sleepiness in patients with Parkinson disease and sleep apnea. *Sleep*. 2014;37:177–85.
82. Kaminska M, Mery VP, Lafontaine A-L, Robinson A, Benedetti A, Gros P, Kimoff RJ. Change in cognition and other non-motor symptoms with obstructive sleep apnea treatment in Parkinson disease. *J Clin Sleep Med*. 2018;14:819–28.
83. Terzaghi M., Spelta L., Minafra B., Rustioni V., Zangaglia R., Pacchetti C., Manni R. Treating sleep apnea in Parkinson's disease with C-PAP: Feasibility concerns and effects on cognition and alertness. *Sleep Med*. 2017;33:114–118.
84. Castel M., De Cock V.C., Léon H., Dupuy-Bonafé I. Mandibular Advancement Device in Parkinson's disease: A pilot study on efficacy and usability. *Sleep Med*. 2019;66:78–81.
85. Videnovic A. Management of sleep disorders in Parkinson's disease and multiple system atrophy. *Movement Disorders*. 2017 May;32(5):659-68
86. Rutten S, Vriend C, Smit JH, Berendse HW, Van Someren EJ, Hoogendoorn AW, Twisk JW, Van Der Werf YD, Van Den Heuvel OA. Bright light therapy for depression in Parkinson disease: a randomized controlled trial. *Neurology*. 2019 Mar 12;92(11):e1145-56.